

Negotiating knowledge by referring to search: exploring the verb ‘to google’ in Swedish online discussions on the climate

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1. Introduction

The verb ‘to google’ is coined after a highly popular search engine set as default in many devices and browsers; but it is also a powerful and often invisible knowledge intermediary (Haider & Sundin, 2019). The verb is however often understood to be synonymous with online search at large (Kilgarriff, 2010); it is increasingly used in everyday online and offline discourse, and often used in first person as relating to an intention to search and thus to some need for insight or information (e.g. “I will google this”). A few studies also investigate search directives, which refers to the suggestion of using a (sometimes specific) search engine and a specific query (e.g. “google the news!”) (Robertson et al., 2023; Rödl & Haider, 2025). The diverse uses and contexts of application of the verb ‘to google’ can provide a different angle to study the social significance of online search.

With search engines understood as knowledge intermediaries, this contribution analyses uses of the verb ‘to google’ to explore what counts as ‘knowledge’ in online discourse where knowledge is contested. Concretely, this research investigates: (1) how is ‘googling’ invoked in online discourse (syntactically and semantically); and (2) how do these references to ‘googling’ negotiate knowledge?

2. Methodology

Because the climate crisis is explored scientifically in ever greater detail but its urgency is also increasingly politicised, debated, or denied in various parts of the population and thriving on the internet (e.g. Dunlap & Brulle, 2020; Harvey et al., 2018), it provides a useful example to investigate how the verb ‘to google’ is used to negotiate what counts as knowledge. The paper does so in the Swedish context, among others because of the different spelling of the platform (‘Google’) and the verb (sv: ‘att googla’)—since 2003 an official part of the Swedish language—, which enables convenient research about this. In Summer 2022, I collected uses of the verb ‘to google’ in various conjugations and composita posted in any of four Swedish online sources between 2014 and summer 2022 by utilising full text search. The sites include two different blogs engaged in climate denial and climate obstruction¹, as well as comments posted there (267 and 568 mentions respectively); the Climate section of an established Swedish online forum² where serious debates and conspiracies co-exist (342); and Swedish-language comments from the old Twitter³ (92). After removing duplicates, quotes, and mentions regarding unrelated issues, a random selection of around half of the mentions were analysed using systematic coding which combines, firstly, abductive content analysis of grammatical and syntactical features and the degree to which a claim was visibly engaged in climate denial obstruction, and secondly, thematic analysis of the semantics and its interactional context.

3. Results

Broadly, there are two ways to conceptualise ‘googling’ based on its conjugation: as a search instruction marked through the imperative (‘Google!’), or as an action marked through any other form; both are coded in almost equal amounts in the data, but are not spread equally across research sites. The

imperative is strongly connected to suggestions to 'do your own research' (with explicit mention of

keyphrases especially in one blog; everywhere else often with more implicit instructions) which is regularly used to spread conspiracy theories (Tripodi et al., 2023), while actions often describe the commenter's or someone else's interaction with the search engine. Based on the thematic analysis and spanning imperative and action forms of the verb 'to google', there appear to be four overall discursive functions of invoking it; they render 'to google' as follows:

1. **to search online with a specific goal:** suggests that knowledge emerges from or can be validated through 'doing' search. Search here is a goal-oriented everyday activity that within an open-ended process can fail, succeed, or be anticipatory, and may focus on both search engine results pages and counts or the search results themselves. For example:
 - "What is the emissivity of the atmosphere? Yes, if you google, you will find values as low as 0.4 up to 0.9."
 - "Try googling "explanation greenhouse effect" and see if any/all of the 20 million hits suit you."
2. **to 'do your own research' on a specific topic:** suggests that 'true' knowledge is hidden but can be revealed through 'digging' with a search engine. This usually means to nudge others out of their established understanding through imperative form, but is also used as a contextualisation of how some supposedly secret insights were made visible through search. For example:
 - "Google rainforest fires and you'll see what no one else wants you to see."
 - "If you google you have to look very far down, google hides most things that do not fit the alarmists."
3. **to obtain insights approved in the context:** suggests that to find 'correct' knowledge is a skill. Search means to identify community-specific insights, and is a marker of both digital citizenship and community belonging. For example:
 - "I gave you examples of how insects can benefit from warming. You can easily google what you are asking for."
 - "Can't find anything when I google... Any good search phrase?"
4. **to bring about supposed evidence:** suggests that 'actual' knowledge requires more than just using a search engine. Search is understood to give rise to flawed evidence claims that are construed through using keyphrases and digital information infrastructure in a specific way that prefigures the outcome. For example:
 - "Instead of desperately googling around on your alarmist blogs, I suggest you read [person]'s own account on [blog]."
 - "Well now you can google something that contradicts my article, and I can google back."

4. Concluding Discussion

As part of online discourse, the verb 'to google' appears an essential feature to negotiate, cultivate, and contest what counts as "knowledge" on climate change and beyond. In line with existing understandings of search practices (Haider & Sundin, 2019), the verb use goes well beyond finding information: It highlights how online sources are strategically used for a variety of knowledge claims; how search skills or capacities are used to mark identity and community belonging in specific online communities; and how 'googling' makes knowledge contestable. Given the novel methodological approach and the importance of the research context for societal futures, these insights are important additions to understand the social significance and embeddedness of online search and its role in knowledge negotiation.

5. Endnotes

1. klimatupplysningen.se, klimatsans.com
2. flashback.org, Query: *googla*, Forum: *Klimat, miljö och geovetenskap*
3. twitter.com, Query: "googla" "klimat" lang:sv since:2014-01-01

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